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MicroRNAs activated during TNBC resistance.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

This included among multiple microRNAs including miR-4521, four separate miR6724 family microRNAs, miR-12136, and miR7845.